

PEDAGOGICAL FEATURES OF DEVELOPING TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL-METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING IN THE QUALIFICATION IMPROVEMENT SYSTEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14552909>

Abstract. *The article deals with the problems of the improvement of professional and methodic preparedness of teachers.*

Keywords: *teacher's Professional Competence and Professional Ability, Teachers' Methodological Training, Independent Professional Development.*

In today's educational system development process, improving teachers' professional readiness has become a pressing issue. Global educational trends increase the need for teachers to continuously improve themselves in a constantly changing world. New pedagogical technologies, innovative teaching methods, and adaptation to international standards are all important factors for teachers' professional development. Today's students stand out for their high demands for knowledge. Teachers must continuously improve their knowledge and skills to meet these needs, effectively teach new knowledge, and develop students' creative abilities.

The modern education system requires teachers not only to possess theoretical knowledge but also to apply innovative methods, work with teams, and demonstrate high competence in solving complex pedagogical tasks. Therefore, it is crucial to analyze the pedagogical features of developing teachers' professional-methodological readiness in the system of professional development. To effectively organize these processes, the following pedagogical features need to be considered:

Personalized Approach. It is necessary to consider the individual characteristics, professional experience, and methodological knowledge levels of each teacher. Identifying teachers' needs through personalized learning paths and shaping educational programs based on these needs is important.

Use of Modern Pedagogical Technologies. Conducting lessons based on interactive and information technologies. Utilizing distance learning platforms, preparing electronic educational materials, and implementing them in practice.

Harmonizing Scientific and Practical Approaches. Harmonizing theory and practical training in the educational process. Involving teachers in scientific-research activities, such as participating in projects aimed at improving modern teaching methods or enhancing the effectiveness of the education system.

Continuity and Systematic Nature of Education. Teachers' professional development must be organized continuously. Educational programs should be developed systematically, step by step, for each subject or field.

Creating a Collaborative Environment. Creating conditions for professional communication among teachers. Strengthening collaboration through experience exchange, professional development clubs, or participation in seminars.

Innovative Approaches. Introducing modern educational materials, skills, and tools for professional development. Deepening the study and application of digitalization processes in education.

Reflective Approach. Analyzing teacher's activities through reflection after learning process. Identifying strengths and weaknesses and determining directions for improvement.

Assessing the Quality of Education. This involves continuous monitoring and evaluation to ensure the effectiveness and quality of learning process.

The introduction of a regular assessment system for teachers' professional readiness is of great importance for improving the quality of the education process and enhancing students' learning outcomes. Based on the assessment results, necessary adjustments to the curriculum can be made, improving the effectiveness of developing teachers' professional-methodological readiness. This system is aimed at consistently supporting teachers, enhancing their scientific-methodological literacy, and promoting the adoption of modern approaches in education.

The professional development system focuses on the following main tasks:

Deepening teachers' pedagogical and methodological knowledge;

Developing skills in using innovative technologies;

Enhancing the ability to meet individual and social needs in education.

Continuous learning is the key to improving education quality and advancing students' learning processes. It is crucial to provide programs aimed at professional development and increase teachers' motivation to learn. Strengthening collaboration between educational institutions, government agencies, and the public is essential for teachers' professional growth.

In conclusion, developing teachers' professional-methodological readiness requires a continuous and systematic approach. Personalization, interactive methods, innovative technologies, and reflection play a key role in the professional development process. These approaches not only enhance the teacher's effectiveness but also improve the overall efficiency of the educational process.

CONCLUSION

The development of teachers' professional-methodological training within the qualification improvement system is essential for enhancing educational quality and effectiveness.

1. Integration of Theory and Practice: Effective professional-methodological training should bridge the gap between educational theory and practical application. This ensures that teachers are not only knowledgeable but also can implement innovative teaching strategies in the classroom.

2. Continuous Professional Development: The qualification improvement system should promote lifelong learning. Regular workshops, seminars, and courses that update teachers on the latest pedagogical trends and technologies are crucial for ongoing professional growth.

3. Collaborative Learning: Encouraging collaboration among teachers fosters sharing of best practices and collective problem-solving. Creating communities of practice can enhance teachers' methodological skills and build a supportive network.

4. Adaptability and Flexibility: Training programs must be adaptable to meet the diverse needs of teachers. Personalizing professional development can help address individual challenges and professional aspirations.

5. **Assessment and Feedback:** Implementing robust assessment mechanisms to evaluate the effectiveness of training programs is vital. Continuous feedback from participants can help refine and improve the training process.

6. **Focus on Student Outcomes:** Ultimately, the goal of teachers' professional-methodological training should be to enhance student learning outcomes. Training should be aligned with educational goals and the needs of students.

In conclusion, the pedagogical features of developing teachers' professional-methodological training are fundamental to fostering a responsive and effective educational environment. By focusing on integration, collaboration, adaptability, and assessment, the qualification improvement system can significantly enhance teachers' capabilities and, consequently, student success.

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